

THE CATEGORY OF GENDER AND “THE NEW WOMEN'S MOVEMENT”

Sheraliyeva Nodirakhon Abduvokhid qizi

A doctoral student of KSPI

+ 99891 155 2333

nodiraxon.sheraliyeva@gmail.com<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8118997>

Annotation. This article is devoted to the study of stereotypes of speech behavior of women, taking into account the social factors of gender, age and type of education that influence the formation of these stereotypes, as well as the analysis of their manifestations in real communication.

Key words: speech behavior, feminist language, gender, discourse, socialization, “female language”.

Introduction

With the beginning of the dominance of postmodernism, the issue of language and gender has become especially relevant, since all the directions that postmodernism is represented have several common features, one of which is the “language concept of reality” [1: 11]. According to this concept, reality is a phenomenon created by language, and a person perceives reality through the prism of his language and its stereotypes. Thus, much attention of postmodernists is paid to language and linguistics, since language within the framework of postmodernism is seen as a means of access to knowledge about non-linguistic phenomena.

Materials and methods. In the late 60s and early 70s of the twentieth century, the New Women's Movement actively declared itself, which gave a powerful impetus to the development of gender studies. The movement originated in the United States and a little later found a response in Germany, where the University of Konstanz became the center of research. Thanks to the emergence of new socio-philosophical ideas, the democratization of society and the student revolution of 1968, representatives of the new movement entered the fight against patriarchy and used the gender concept of male dominance in the political struggle. The new women's movement gave a powerful impetus to the development of gender studies, and it was then that several new directions in linguistics arose, one of which was feminist language criticism, or feminist linguistics. The main criticism of feminist linguistics has been directed at the androcentricity of society in general and language in particular. The language was accused of sexism and discrimination against women, which, in their opinion, was expressed in the predominance of masculine forms in the language, the objectivity and secondary nature of women. In addition, supporters of feminist linguistics argued that gender is one of the most important factors influencing the construction of communication. The feminist critique of language was aimed not just at pointing out the fact of sexism and discrimination, but saw the main goal of combating them and changing the language. The idea of the need to reform the language was based on the Sapir-Whorf hypothesis of linguistic relativity. The hypothesis was put forward in the 1930s by B.L. Whorf, who relied on the ideas of E. Sapir. The essence of the hypothesis is that representatives of different cultures, speaking different languages, perceive the world differently, that is, the perception of the world and, accordingly, thinking are determined by the language of the speaker. The world is perceived by a person through the prism of the native language, the system of models of which organizes the impressions received from the surrounding world in the mind of this person.

Feminist studies of that time can be roughly divided into two main groups. The goal of the first group was to reveal “asymmetries in the language system directed against women” [Glossary of Gender Terms 2002], that is, to prove the sexism of the language. The purpose of the second group was to explore the features of communication in mixed and same-sex groups on a wide range of material, such as television talk shows, family communication, doctor-patient dialogues. Research in this area is based on the assumption that behavioral strategies, including speech ones, are based on stereotypes fixed in the language. Most of the researchers were engaged in the search and study of language asymmetries. Based on the theory of Sapir-Whorf, representatives of feminist linguistics actively insist on changing linguistic norms, considering this the goal of their research, which should lead to equality between men and women both in language and in life.

Research and discussion

In Germany, the most famous were the works of S. Tremel-Ploetz "Linguistik und Frauensprache" ("Linguistics and Women's Language") [4:33] and L. Push "Das Deutsche als Männersprache" ("German is the language of men"). The authors of these works were the first to draw attention to the problem of the relationship between gender and gender in the language on the material of the German language, and also raised the question of the neutrality of masculine nouns when denoting people, since in many contexts, despite the fact that we are talking about a woman, masculine names and pronouns are used. In the USA, one of the fundamental works of feminist linguistics was R. Lakoff's book "Language and the Place of Woman", published in 1973. R. Lakoff was one of the first to talk about the asymmetry of the images of men and women in the picture of the world, and, accordingly, in the linguistic picture of the world. The main goal of the work was to show that the language reflects the dominant position of a man and the image of a woman's inferiority, appearing in the linguistic picture of the world. R. Lakoff developed her own methodology, based not only on linguistics, but also on other sciences, such as psychology, sociology, anthropology, history, etc. The work is of a vivid polemical nature and contains ideas of possible influence on language policy [3:51]. R. Lakoff also considered the question of the existence of a “female language” and suggested that the “female language” is absorbed by girls in childhood in the process of socialization, just like the behavior that befits a girl, expressing symbolic weakness and subordination: playing with dolls, refusal of rough games, rude vocabulary, willingness to give in, seem less aggressive. According to R. Lakoff, the “female language” is characterized by the use of linguistic means that reduce the power of statements, the rejection of rude language, etc. As J. Coats points out in *Women, Men and Language*, many of the thoughts expressed by R. Lakoff about women's speech are close to O. Jespersen's ideas about the features of the language used by female representatives [2: 52-53]. The work of R. Lakoff, as well as the work of O. Jespersen, was later criticized a lot for the lack of an analyzed representative material. In addition, a certain social group of women was accepted as the norm - white English-speaking residents of the United States of the middle class. Despite the limited description of the features of the speech of American women, the work of R. Lakoff sets out the general position that naive-linguistic ideas about female speech create a picture of the norms of femininity in a particular society, that is, representatives of a certain society consider the speech style used by women, an indicator of what women are. That is, in Western society the female speech style is characterized by a decrease in the power of statements and the non-use of coarse

vocabulary, then ideas about femininity will be appropriate. Like the work of R. Lakoff, many works written within the framework of feminist linguistics have been seriously criticized, since empirical studies of the gender aspects of communication have shown that feminist linguistics has made a number of methodological errors, such as: attributing excessive significance to the gender factor, intentionalism, ignoring the context, underestimating qualitative research methods.

Conclusion

Feminist studies, especially of the early stage, gave too much importance to gender, considering it a factor that determines the self-identification of a person. Although the positions and approaches of feminist linguistics were criticized, nevertheless, its successes in the field of language policy were very serious.

References:

1. Gender as an intrigue of knowledge. Collection of articles, comp. Kirilina A.V. M., 2000.
2. Kirilina 1997 - Kirilina A.V. Category "gender" in linguistics. 1997. No. 2. M., 1997.
3. Lakoff 1975 – Lakoff R. Language and Woman's Place. New York, 1975.
4. Troemel-Ploetz 1983 – Troemel-Ploetz S. Feminismus und Linguistics // Feminismus. Inspektion einer Herrenkultur. Frankfurt am Main, 1983.
5. Azizova Moxinur Muzaffarjon kizi. (2023). LANGUAGE AND CULTURE. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact Factor: 7.429, 12(04), 29–31. Retrieved from <https://www.gejournal.net/index.php/IJSSIR/article/view/1708>
6. Azizova Moxinur Muzaffarjon kizi. (2022). "TOAST" CONCEPT IN DIFFERENT LANGUAGE SYSTEM. Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal, 10(12), 1472–1477. Retrieved from <https://internationaljournals.co.in/index.php/giirj/article/view/3283>
7. Mansurovna, M. A. D. (2022). The Book Of "Erewhon" As A Glory Of A Young Writer. Journal of Pharmaceutical Negative Results, 3540-3543.
8. Мухиддинова, Д. (2022). ВЕЛИКИЕ УТОПИЧЕСКИЕ ВЗГЛЯДЫ СЭМЬЮЭЛА БАТЛЕРА THE GREAT UTOPIAN VIEWS OF SAMUEL BUTLER SAMUEL BATLERNING BUYUK UTOPIK QARASHLARI. Zamonaviy dunyoda innovatsion tadqiqotlar: Nazariya va amaliyot, 1(28), 270-272.
9. Mansurovna, M. A. D. (2022). IMAGES OF THE NOVEL "EREVON". Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal, 10(12), 816-819.
10. Muxitdinova, D. (2022). THE ISSUES OF THE MODERN BUTLERIANA.
11. Muxitdinova, D. (2022). Images of the novel Erevon.
12. Ochildiyeva, H. (2023). MODERN FOREIGN LANGUAGE PERSPECTIVES ON CREATIVITY.
13. Ochildiyeva, H. (2022). THE IMPORTANCE OF INNOVATIVE EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING THE SUBJECT OF THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE.
14. Ochildiyeva, H. (2022). Lexical and grammatical categories of nouns.
15. Ochildiyeva, H. (2022). Lexical and Phraseological Means of Expressing Ethical Evaluation of a Person in Russian and Uzbek Languages.
16. Ochildiyeva, H. (2022). SYSTEM OF WORK ON USE INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES AT THE CLASSES OF RUSSIAN LANGUAGE AND

LITERATURE FOR THE PURPOSE DEVELOPMENT OF RUSSIAN SPEECH OF YOUTH STUDENTS.

17. Muxtarovna, A. D. (2022). DIDACTIC PRINCIPLES OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION CHILD LIFE. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11(12), 178-182.

18. Alixonova, D. M. (2021). THE SOCIAL AND PEDAGOGICAL ASPECTS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOLERANCE IN THE FAMILY. Academic research in educational sciences, 2(6), 1335-1338.

19. **THE FACTORS AND TRENDS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOLERANCE IN THE FAMILY**
Alixonova Dilbar Muxtarovna, Kasimova Nodira Inomovna
doi: [10.48047/ecb/2023.12.si4.11992023.27/05/2023](https://doi.org/10.48047/ecb/2023.12.si4.11992023.27/05/2023)

20. Ochildiyeva, H. (2022). Lexical and Phraseological Means of Expressing Ethical Evaluation of a Person in Russian and Uzbek Languages. MIDDLE EUROPEAN 120 SCIENTIFIC BULLETIN.

21. Rajapova, M. (2021). BADIY DISKURSDA KOGNITIV METAFORALARNING ISHLATILISHI. Scienceweb academic papers collection.

22. Malika, R. (2021). ISSN: 2249-7137 Vol. 11.

INNOVATIVE
ACADEMY